

Evaluation of antimicrobial and diuretic activities of some new synthesized : 5-(substituted arylidenes)-2-(substituted aryl)-3-(4-nitrophenoxy acetamido)- 4-oxo-thiazolidines derivatives

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Abstract : Twenty seven new arylidino phenoxy acetamido 4-oxo-thiazolidine derivatives were synthesized and evaluated for their antimicrobial and diuretic activities. The structures of all newly synthesized compounds have been determined by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectroscopic techniques. Some of the compounds shows good pharmacological results.

Keywords : Antimicrobial, diuretic, nitrophenoxy acetamido thiazolidines.

Introduction

Various 4-oxo-thiazolidines have been known to possess various pharmacological properties such as antifungal, antibacterial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, anticonvulsant, anthelmintic¹ etc. Phenoxy group has been also present in many therapeutically useful heterocyclic compounds². Hence, it was thought that a 4-oxo-thiazolidine ring if coupled to a phenoxy moiety, the resulting compound might possess enhanced pharmacological activity. In view of this thought, we have synthesized some new compounds and evaluated their pharmacological activity.

Results and discussion

Equimolar solution of ethyl chloroacetate was added to a solution of 4-nitrophenol giving 4-nitrophenoxy ethyl acetate, **1** which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate yielded 4-nitrophenoxy acetylhydrazide **2**. The compound **2** on condensation with various selected aromatic aldehydes afforded *N*-substituted aryl-4-nitrophenoxy aryl hydrazide, **3a-i** which on cycloaddition with thioglycolic acid gave 2-(substituted aryl)-3-(4-nitrophenoxy acetamido)-4-oxo-thiazolidines, **4a-i**. Treatment of 4-oxo-thiazolidine **4a-i** with various aromatic aldehydes give 5-(substituted arylidenes)-2-(substituted aryl)-3-(4-nitrophenoxy acetamido)-4-oxo-thiazolidines, **5a-i** (Scheme 1).

All the new synthesized compounds **3a-i**, **4a-i** and **5a-i** were evaluated for their antibacterial activities against

Salmonella typhimurium (*St*), *Bacillus subtilis* (*Bs*), *Shigella dysenteriae* (*Sd*) and *Escherichia coli* (*Ec*) at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations by filter paper disc method³. Standard streptomycin was also tested at the same conditions for comparison. Compounds **3a-i**, **4a-i** and **5a-i** were also screened for their antifungal activity against *Rizopus oryzae* (*Ro*), *Cryosporium panical* (*Cp*) and *Candida albicans* (*Ca*) at 50, 100 and 500 ppm concentrations by filter paper disc method³. Standard antifungal griseofulvin was also tested at same conditions for comparison. The results of active compounds of **3a-i**, **4a-i** and **5a-i** of antibacterial and antifungal activities are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Diuretic activity of the compounds **3a-i**, **4a-i** and **5a-i** was tested by Lipschitz method^{4,5} in adult male rats fasted overnight with free access to water loaded orally with 5 mL/100 g bw normal saline. All the test compounds (50 mg/kg oral) and standard drug and furosemide at a dose of 30 mg/kg (oral) suspended in 0.5% gum acacia and administered to the animals of respective groups in a volume of 5 mL/100 g. One group of animals was taken as control. All animals were used once a week. The urine flow was in order of 1 mL/h/rat. The results are shown in Table 4.

These pharmacological evaluation are based on structure activity relationship, it has been demonstrated that the introduction of halogen atoms particularly bromine in benzene ring enhanced the pharmacological activity.

Other groups like nitro or amino or methoxy in the benzene ring show less activity than the bromine atom.

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of the representative compounds

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	NMR (δ)
3b	67	142	4.69 (2H, s, OCH ₂ , N=CH), 6.75–7.88 (8H, m, Ar-H)
3e	69	141	4.63 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.77–7.82 (8H, m, Ar-H)
3h	72	154	4.69 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.76–7.80 (8H, m, Ar-H)
3i	58	179	4.65 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.77–6.86 (8H, m, Ar-H)
4c	65	147	3.09 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 3.59 (2H, s, CH ₂ S), 4.77 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.67–7.89 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.93 (1H, s, CONH)
4e	72	169	3.00 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 3.55 (2H, s, CH ₂ S), 4.79 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.67–7.80 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.89 (1H, s, CONH)
4h	78	193	3.15 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 3.55 (2H, s, CH ₂ S), 4.79 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.74–7.86 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.91 (1H, s, CONH)
4i	73	210	3.16 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 3.43 (2H, s, CH ₂ S), 4.25 (6H, s, N(CH ₃) ₂), 4.65 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.80–7.90 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, s, CONH)
5d	63	172	3.18 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 4.75 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.28 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 6.73–7.88 (14H, m, Ar-H), 7.82 (1H, s, CONH)
5e	69	184	3.16 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 4.77 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.25 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 6.70–7.85 (14H, m, Ar-H), 7.83 (1H, s, CONH)
5h	71	178	3.18 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 3.87 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃ , Ar-OCH ₃), 4.81 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.23 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 6.79–7.88 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.87 (1H, s, CONH)
5j	75	194	3.17 (1H, s, -N-CH-Ar), 4.79 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.27 (12H, s, 2 × N(CH ₃) ₂), 5.27 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 6.67–7.83 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.83 (1H, s, CONH)

Table 2. Antibacterial screening result of the active compounds

Compd.	<i>S. typhimurium</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>S. dysenteriae</i>	
3e	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++
4c	++	++	+++	+++	++	+++
4d	++	+++	++	++	+++	+++
4e	+++	+++	++	++	++	+++
4f	++	+++	++	+++	++	++
5d	++	++	++	+++	++	++
5f	++	+++	++	++	++	++++
5g	+++	+++	++	+++	++	++++
5m	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

Sm = Streptomycin, inhibition diameter in mm : (-) 5–8; (+) 8–14; (++) 14–18; (+++) 18–24; (++++) 24–30.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries. IR spectra recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The ¹H NMR spectra recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a Zeol instrument. The purity of the compounds was monitored on TLC plates.

4-Nitrophenoxy ethyl acetate (1) :

Equimolar solution of 4-nitrophenol (0.1 mol) and ethylchloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (4.96 g) was refluxed on a water bath for about 8 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the solid thus obtained was filtered and dried. It was purified over the column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (4 : 6 v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallized from ethanol to given compound **1**, yield (82%), m.p. 143–145 °C (Found : C, 53.28; H, 4.80; N, 6.13. C₁₀H₁₁NO₅ Calcd : C, 53.33; H, 4.89; N, 6.23%); ν_{max} (principal absorptions) : 3016, 1671, 1509, 763, 695 (aromatic ring), 2912, 2882, 1423 and 712 (CH₂ and CH₃), 1529, 1321 (Ar-NO₂), 1725 (C=O ester), 1241, 1190 and 1172 (C–O–C) cm⁻¹; δ 1.24 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, -COOCH₂CH₃), 4.26 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.68 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.87–7.79 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS : 225 (M⁺), 180, 123, 77.

4-Nitrophenoxy acetyl hydrazine (2) :

A mixture of nitrophenoxy ethylacetate **1** (0.04 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.04 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about 5 h. The excess of

Table 3. Antifungal screening result of the active compounds

Compd	<i>R. oryzae</i>			<i>C. parvial</i>			<i>C. alabicans</i>		
	-	++	++	-	+	++	++	++	+++
3c	-	++	++	-	+	++	++	++	+++
3g	+	++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
4d	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
4e	++	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
4f	++	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
4g	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
5d	++	++	+++	++	+++	++	++	++	++
5g	++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
GF	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+++	++	+++	+++

GF = Griseofulvin, inhibition diameter in mm (-) 6-8, (+) 8-13, (++) 13-16, (+++) 16-23, (++++) 23-29

solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the solid thus obtained was filtered and dried. It was purified over the column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (6 : 4 v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallized from methanol to give compound **2**, yield (69%), m.p. 158 °C (Found : C, 45.36; H, 4.16; N, 19.87. $C_8H_9N_3O_4$ Calcd : C, 45.50; H, 4.27; N, 19.90%); ν_{max} 1672 (>C=O, amido) cm^{-1} ; δ 4.25 (2H, s, -NH₂), 4.71 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 7.99 (1H, s, -CONH), 6.99-7.80 (4H, m, Ar-H); MS : 211 (M⁺), 80, 77, 31.

N-Benzylidene-4-nitrophenoxy-acetylhydrazide (**3a**) :

A mixture of 4-nitrophenoxy-acetylhydrazine (0.02 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.02 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) with 5-6 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a steam bath for about 8 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the solid thus obtained was filtered and dried. It was purified over the column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (5 : 5 v/v) as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallized from methanol to give compound **3a**, yield (76%) m.p. 137-139 °C (Found : C, 63.22; H, 4.10; N, 9.65. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3O_4$ Calcd : C, 63.38; H, 4.22; N, 9.85%); ν_{max} 1627 (-N=CH) cm^{-1} ; δ 4.69 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 7.90 (1H, s, -CONH), 6.70-7.88 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.93 (1H, s, N=CH); MS : 299 (M⁺), 209, 90, 77.

Other compounds **3b-i** were synthesized in a similar manner using various aromatic aldehydes (Table 4.)

2-Benzylidene-3-(4-nitrophenoxyacetamido)-4-oxo-thiazolidine (**4a**) :

Table 4. Diuretic screening result of the active compounds

Compd	Normal saline loaded (5 ml/100 g b w)	Urine output	% Output	Diuretic activity
3a	47 56	12 42	26 11	39 11
3c	48 89	13 90	28 37	42 61
3d	48 57	12 99	26 74	40 16
3f	46 12	13 79	29 90	44 30
3g	48 12	11 99	24 91	37 42
3i	49 37	14 00	28 35	42 59
4a	46 70	11 05	23 66	35 53
4b	49 58	11 17	22 52	33 83
4e	46 76	12 00	25 66	38 54
4g	46 18	11 12	24 07	36 16
5a	47 12	13 57	28 79	43 25
5f	49 30	11 67	23 67	35 55
5h	46 90	11 10	23 66	35 54
Furosemide	48 80	32 16	66 58	-
Control	48 60	7 54	15 61	-

A mixture of compound **3a** (0.01 mol) in thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl₂ was refluxed on a water bath for about 9 h. The solvent was removed to get the product. It was passed through a column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol (8 : 2 v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallised from methanol to give **4a**, yield (78%) m.p. 172-174 °C (Found : C, 54.57; H, 3.97; N, 11.13. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_5S$ Calcd : C, 54.67; H, 4.02; N, 11.21%); ν_{max} 3334, 1431 (-NH), 2975 (-N-CH-S), 1716 (>C=O, cyclic), 1670 (C=O amido) cm^{-1} ; δ 3.11 (1H, s, N-CH-Ar), 3.61 (2H, s, -CH₂S), 4.66 (2H, s, -OCH₂),

Compd	Ar	Ar ¹
3,4,5b	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5c	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	3-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5e	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	2-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5f	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	3-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5g	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄
3,4,5h	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄
3,4,5i	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) ClCH₂COOC₂H₅, (ii) NH₂NH₂, (iii) ArCHO, (iv) SHCH₂COOH, (v) Ar¹CHO

7.95 (1H, s, -CONH), 6.71–7.85 (9H, m, Ar-H); MS : 373 (M⁺), 180, 161, 119, 115, 90, 77.

Other compounds **4b-i** were synthesized in a similar manner using **3b-i** as starting material.

5-(Benzylidine)-2-(phenyl)-3-(4-nitrophenoxy acetamido)-4-oxo-thiazolidines (5a) :

Equimolar solution of **4a** (0.04 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.004 mol) in methanol (35 ml) in the presence of C₂H₅ONa were refluxed for about 7 h on a water bath and cooled. The solvent was removed to get a solid product. It was passed through a column of silica gel using benzene : chloroform (4 : 6 v/v) mixture as eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was recrystallized from ethanol to afford **5a**, yield (68%), m.p. 157–159 °C (Found : C, 62.39; H, 4.07; N, 9.08. C₂₄H₁₉N₃O₅S Calcd. : C, 62.45; H, 4.12; N, 9.11%); ν_{max} 1630 (>C=CH-Ar) cm⁻¹; δ 3.10 (1H, s, N-CH-Ar) 3.18 (1H, s, -CH₂S), 4.47 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.73–7.88 (14H, m, Ar-H), 5.23 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar); MS : 461 (M⁺), 339, 249, 224, 180, 159.

Similarly, other thiazolidines **5b-i** were synthesized from **4b-i** and their physical data are given in Table 1.

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